

Clinical Approaches to Assess Neurological Outcomes of Cardiopulmonary Arrest in Unconscious Adults

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Abstract

Background

Current guidelines to predicting 'poor' neurological outcome in post-arrest unconscious adults have not previously been analysed in detail and, authoritative guidance to prediction of 'good' neuroprognosis does not exist.

Methods

A narrative appraisal of guideline statements and presented clinical indices of 'poor' neuroprognosis and, a systematic review of reported bedside indicators of 'good' outcome.

Results

The overall quality of neuroprognostication studies is low.

Current neuroprognostication guidelines focus exclusively on predicting 'poor' outcome of post-CA unconsciousness by static clinical and/or paraclinical tests 3-5 days after ROSC and yield indirect evidence only. The approach is weakened also because acknowledged 'poor' outcome signs can be indistinguishable from features of natural brain revival towards intact neurological survival.

Guidelines do not address 'good' outcome indicators.

Twenty-one studies on 'good' outcome parameters were identified. Eleven were of low or very low quality of evidence and ten studies poorer. Inclusion of individuals about-to or already-awake presumably biased 12 studies.

However, the order, recovery rate and linkage of clinical features seem essential for monitoring and predicting the brain resuscitation course after cardiopulmonary arrest. Unconscious patients likely to make 'good' recoveries can be discerned from those with 'poor' neuro-perspectives by cranial nerve reflex findings during BLS and within 60 min from ROSC or by the results of cranial nerve reflex-, motor responses to 'pain'- and EEG investigations within the first few hours from ROSC.

Patient's neurological performances or quality of life scores at best after awakening seem rational prognostication endpoints.

Conclusion

Serial bedside investigations deployed within minutes to a few hours during unconsciousness and longitudinal surveillance of patient's neurological faculties and quality of life scores after awakening are suggested to improve neuroprognostication in adults resuscitated from cardiopulmonary arrest.

Introduction

Clinical measures to predicting 'poor' * neurological outcomes in adults left unconscious after cardiopulmonary arrest with global body ischaemia (CA) have not changed significantly in step with the increased public involvement in basic life support (BLS) and progresses of post-resuscitation care, e.g. myocardial re-vascularisation and therapeutic hypothermia (TH) with sedation, analgesia and neuromuscular blockade (THect).

The current guidelines (CG), issued in 2015 ¹⁻³, rely on previously established solitary 'poor' outcome (PO) parameters ^{4,5} but recommend the use of more clinical and/or paraclinical tests in combination to predict neuroprognosis.

CG do not define coma and do not address 'good' outcome (GO) indicators.

We analysed CG statements and the neurological and neurophysiological prognosticators of PO acknowledged by the guidelines and reviewed reports on clinical GO indicators systematically. New neuroprognostication strategies are suggested.

* single quotation marks indicate inaccurate expressions, double marks frame precise quotations

Methods

We did not review the literature on the PO predictors that supports CG but provide a narrative appraisal of the CG statements and of currently acknowledged bedside parameters to predicting PO.

We identified 1507 PubMed indexed GO studies from January 1974 to August 2019. The initial search criteria were "cardiac arrest", "resuscitation" and "neurological outcome". Further search build-ups, by adding the criterion "neurological examination" or "conventional electroencephalography" or "good neurological outcome" or "good neurological outcome prediction", provided 426, 353, 124 and 84 citations, respectively. Studies of post-CA unconsciousness with GO in adults were identified and appraised according to the PRISMA guidelines⁶.

The primary search provided 15 and the extended searches five citations when duplicates were excluded. From the reference lists in these 20 papers, we identified further seven relevant articles. Thus, 27 full-text reports were initially eligible for appraisal.

Excluded were reports on CA in children, CA due to poisoning or trauma, reports on non-neurological indicators, case-stories, papers on not-conventionally treated CA, studies without specified neurological endpoints and reports on brain imaging and biomarkers.

Six of the 27 reports were excluded⁷⁻¹² because indicator- or outcome-characteristics were not described. From the final set of 21 studies, we systematically extracted data on study design, sample size, patient's neurological state when enrolled and investigation-, predictor- and outcome-characteristics.

The GRADE approach¹³ was used to define study design- or execution limitations, inconsistencies, imprecisions or possible sample bias - and to grade quality of evidence (qE).

Results

Analyses of current guidelines

Definition of coma

CG use the words "coma" and "comatose" - but *do not define coma*. The term covers a broad spectrum of functional disorders from no brain function at all to the presence of cranial nerve reflexes (CNR) + motor response to 'pain' (MRP) + activity in the electroencephalogram (EEG) - in the absence of arousal and awareness. Coma should be defined by distinctive neurological findings. The neurology at the time when spontaneous circulation is restored after CA depicts the sum of CA-impacts upon the brain, define the coma state, provide definite clues to the assessment of the brain recovery capability and, give a reference status for comparison with subsequent clinical findings which is important for assessing the brain recovery course and outcome, treatment efficacy and possible influences from confounding factors ¹⁴.

Definition of 'poor' outcome

PO is defined by Cerebral Performance Category Scale (CPCS)-scores ¹⁵ 5-3 (brain death, persistent unconsciousness, vegetative state, severe post-awakening disability) or by modified Rankin Scale (mRS)-scores 6-3 ¹⁶ (death, severe-, moderately severe-, moderate disability).

Neurology of circulatory arrest

We have previously detailed the neurology of CA in patients with CA due to primary heart disease who were not treated by THect ^{17,18}. Our findings were passed on in a too simplified version : "Brain stem reflexes return first, then MPR and finally cortical activity and consciousness" ¹⁹. We found that an initial fixed order of return and exclusive presence of CNR was followed by sequential recoveries of *linked* neurological and EEG features (Table 1). The CNR+MRP+EEG-features evolved within the first 24 h and consciousness returned within less than 72 h (median 17 h and 50 h) in patients who initially had no detectable cortical activity (NoDCA) in the EEG ¹⁸. Patients followed the same recovery route irrespective of their eventual outcomes; but derailed courses were identified by stagnating or incomplete features or by losses of once recovered brain functions or by persistent epileptic phenomena ¹⁴.

The impact of THect on the neurology of CA is virtually unknown. The setting may modify the brain resuscitation course; but, features similar to those outlined above should expectedly emerge prior to THect and after rewarming. Pragmatic approaches to clarify the neurology of CA during THect and rewarming are given lateron.

Table 1. Sequential Features Of The Natural Brain Recovery Course During Post-CA Unconsciousness In Patients Not Treated With Hypothermia

During BLS

- A) Spontaneous respiratory movements
- B) Spontaneous respiratory movements + pupillary light reflex
- C) Spontaneous respiratory movements + pupillary light - + coughing-swallowing reflexes
- D) Spontaneous respiratory movements + pupillary light- + coughing swallowing- + ciliospinal reflexes

After ROSC

- E) Exclusive presence of spontaneous respiratory movements + pupillary light- + coughing swallowing- + ciliospinal reflexes
(: no motor response to 'pain' (*MRP*) and no detectable cortical activity (noDCA) in the EEG)
- F) Spontaneous respiratory movements + pupillary light- + coughing swallowing- + ciliospinal- and caloric vestibular reflexes (*all CNR*) + extensor MPR + noDCA
- G) All CNR + flexor or stereotypic MRP + bursts-suppressions-EEG
- H) All CNR + stereotypic or defensive MRP + continuous cortical activity-EEG

Legend to Table 1. Sequential Features Of The Natural Brain Recovery Course During Post-CA Unconsciousness In Patients Not Treated with Hypothermia

A-D): *recovery of brain stem functions during BLS* occurred independently of whether circulation could be re-established ¹⁷.

Spontaneous respiratory movements were observed or noted as interference with artificial ventilation.

Pupillary reflex constriction was elicited by flashes of 1500 lux ³³.

Coughing-swallowing was provoked by the introduction of a catheter into the larynx and trachea.

Ciliospinal reflex: pupillary dilatation in response to cutaneous stimulation by 1 msec/50 mA current pulses ³³
#

E) Cranial nerve reflexes are exclusively present

F-H): All CNR ^α: respiratory movements, pupillary light-, coughing swallowing-, ciliospinal- and caloric vestibular reflexes (: eyeball movements following irrigation of the external auditory meatus with ice water ³³)).

The E-H recovery *sequence of concurrent CNR, motor responses to pain (MPR) and EEG features* could be observed during BLS ¹⁷ but *most often emerged after ROSC* ¹⁸.

MRP (motor responses to 'pain') elicited by 1 msec/50mA electrical pulses ³³ were: *extensor* (: decerebrate), *flexor* (: decorticate), *stereotypic* (: eyeball rolling, grimacing, non-defensive movements) or *defensive* MPR (: stimulus-localising, -removing or -avoiding response) .

Awakening was signified by defensive MRP, orientating eye movements (fixation and eye-following of objects and persons) and ability to obey simple commands e.g. to move the head or a limb.

Bursts-suppressions and continuous cortical activity EEGs were with or without spikes/sharp waves
Continuous cortical activity evolved from no detectable activity (strictly defined ³⁶) via bursts-suppressions activity within 24 h (median 17 h).

The ciliospinal reflex is but exceptionally utilized in neuroprognostication studies ^{14,17} . If present, noxious stimulation of the skin elicit unilateral dilatation of the pupil. The response is mediated via spinathalamic paths, lateral hypothalamus, midbrain, pons, brain stem and upper thoracal segments of the spinal medulla, the upper cervical ganglion and sympathetic nerve along the carotid artery plexus to the long ciliary nerve which innervates the pupillodilatator muscle of the eye.

^α Corneal- gag- and oculo-cephalic ("doll eye") reflexes were not tested.

CG statements

CG state that brain injury is the main cause of treatment failure and death after CA but add that the plurality of fatalities in ICUs result from active withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment (WLST) - when a 'poor' neurological outcome is anticipated. The use of WLST seems endorsed by the belief that the CA lesion the brain earlier and more severely than other bodily organs e.g. the heart. However, animal experiments have shown that a normal brain can tolerate complete ischaemia for up to 20 min at 37 gC- if the postarrest perfusion is adequate. A 5 min selective and total arrest of the blood supply to a normal heart at normothermia, by contrast, invariably results in pump failure with inadequate perfusion of all vital organs²⁰. Experiences from resuscitation practice corroborate these findings: Eightyfour % of 111 CA-patients presented some brain function during BLS prior to and independent of whether spontaneous circulation could be restored. Failure of re-establishment of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) in patients who recovered some brain function (in two even consciousness) or "dissociated cardiac death" occurred in 24%. Further 16 % of patients suffered cardiogenic shock with final asystole within 24 hours^{17,21}.

The 2010 guidelines maintained that neither neurological nor electrophysiological signs reliably predict the neuroprognosis of coma within the first 24 hours after CA²² and CG "suggest against the use of clinical criteria alone before 72 h from ROSC to estimate neuroprognosis"³.

However, we have established that persistent unconsciousness or severe postawakening disability could be anticipated *at 60 min after start of BLS* if respiratory movements, pupillary light-, coughing swallowing- and pupillary 'pain' (: ciliospinal)- reflexes were not all there or if once recovered reflexes were lost (true positive rate (TPR) 1.0- .94, prior odds .89)¹⁷. Post-ROSC failure of recovery of ciliospinal- or caloric-vestibular-reflexes or of MRP *at 1 h* differentiated patients staying unconscious from those regaining consciousness with TPR 97-.77, prior odds .50 and, absence of linked neurological and EEG features or presence of persistent epileptic phenomena after ROSC suggested poor neurological perspectives¹⁴.

The *THect setting* may certainly blur some aspects of the CA-neurology and prolong the brain resuscitation process²³. But, pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflex-tests are feasible during *THect* and, other CNR and MRP, that may be concealed by sedation and paralysis, can be tested in treatment pauses with short-acting drugs. EEG is not modified by neuromuscular blockade nor by cooling to and re-warming from 33 C^{24,25} whereas sedation may produce bursts-suppressions (BS)²⁶ or slowing or acceleration of cortical activities²⁷. We presume that absence of pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes *during THect* signify PO.

CG state that observation should be prolonged with a *daily* examination of clinical signs when residual sedation and/or paralysis is suspected. However, more frequent checks through the early hrs and days after ROSC would serve to monitor and predict the course of brain resuscitation and to disclose interferences from confounding factors¹⁸. Daily checks are also recommended by CG to "identify a clinical picture suggesting that brain death has occurred". It is generally acknowledged that brain stem function is central to the perception of life and death²⁸. Brain death occurs in < 20% of patients, typically more hours from ROSC²⁹ and secondary to haemodynamic-, respiratory- or metabolic derangements^{17,18,21}. In patients who have no CNR it seems reasonable to test for irreversible apnoea *at any time after ROSC* to declare death - if preconditions are met: Hypothermia and/or sedation and/or primary brain disease must be excluded^{14,28}. Brain death is rarely diagnosed in clinical practice before WLST is decided³⁰.

Currently acknowledged solitary PO-prognosticators

The PO-prognosticators are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Currently acknowledged Prognosticators Of 'Poor' Outcome Of Post-arrest Unconsciousness

Accurate prognosticators

- 1) bilateral absence of pupillary light- and /or corneal reflex 72 h from ROSC or later
- 2) bilateral absence of N20 component of somatosensory evoked potentials within 72 h in noTH- and >72 h from ROSC in TH-patients

Less accurate prognosticators

- 3) no or extensor MRP at 36-108 h from ROSC
- 4) 'myoclonus status' during first 72 h
- 5) high values of serum neuron-specific enolase at 24-72 h
- 6) 'areactive' background activity in the EEG at 72 h or later
- 7) bursts-suppressions EEG at 72 h or after re-warming
- 8) electrographic seizures with a non-reactive background or 'status epilepticus' during TH and after re-warming

Legend to Table 2. Currently acknowledged Prognosticators Of 'Poor' Outcome Of Post- arrest Unconsciousness

Accurate prognosticators are considered '*robust*' due to O false-positive predictive rates with narrow 95% CI

ad 1) when influences of THect have weaned, and other possible confounding factors are excluded

ad 2) *Absence of the N20 wave of short-latency SSEP* (: scalp recordings showing lack of

bilateral cortical responses 20msec after quantified electrical stimulation of a peripheral nerve) predicting PO at

24 h from ROSC in noTH-patients and during the following 48 h; also PO predictive during and after TH

with false-positive rates of 0-4 and 0-3%, respectively

Less accurate prognosticators are characterised by low false-positive rates but broad CI and recommended used in combination with other prognosticators

ad 3) *No or an extensor MRP* is considered useful (due to high sensitivity) when used in conjunction with other PO signs at 72 h or later. European Guidelines: a precondition for the use of a suggested prognostic algorithm in both noTH- and TH-patients ²

ad 4) '*Status myoclonus*' (persisting myoclonies (repetitive muscular jerks >30 min ?)) European Guidelines: within 48 h².

American Heart Association Guidelines: 24-72 h post-arrest in both noTH- and TH-patients ³

ad 5) use of biomarkers is not discussed herein

ad 6) '*areactive*' EEG (: no reproducible changes after deliberate stimulation or 'lack of reactivity') predictive of PO with false-positive rate 1-7 % during TH and 0-3% after re-warming

ad 8) '*status epilepticus*' (: persistent spike/sharp-wave discharges) during and after TH.

American Heart Association guidelines: If intractable and persisting > 72 h in the absence of EEG 'reactivity'; also valid in noTH-patients³. European Guidelines: during TH or immediately after re-warming especially when the background is 'areactive' or discontinuous².

Comments on solitary PO-prognosticators

There are no standards for quantitative testing the *corneal reflex*.

One cannot establish zero or '*absent*' N20 wave of the somatosensory evoked potential (SSEP) - only that no response was detected at a given sensitivity of recording³¹.

No or an extensor MRP (corresponding to Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) motor scores 1-2³²) are early features of natural brain revival (see table 1).

Quantitative 'pain' stimulation to check and reproduce MRP is rarely used in resuscitation practice. Devices delivering defined noxious (electrical) stimuli are available³³.

Myoclonies emerge transiently after CA and do not relate consistently to outcome¹⁸. Persistent myoclonies, however, may depict severe brain dysfunction. There is no consented definition of 'status' and, clinical features may differentiate subtypes compatible with GO³⁴.

Classification of *PO-EEG* differ among studies; but standardisation reduces interrater disagreements³⁵.

Bursts-suppressions (BS) are the earliest sign of natural electro-cortical revival¹⁸ and may, even in the shape of epileptiform activity, be compatible with GO²⁶.

"Status epilepticus" is observed in up to 1/3 of patients, whether treated by TH^{26, 37, 38} or not¹⁸ and most often reflects serious brain dysfunction.

CG do not mention low voltage-EEG (<10 uV) presumably because tracing and interpretation require particular measures. EEG (recorded at high sensitivity to disclose minute cortical activity) unavoidably displays numerous extra-cortical signals³³. Activities may all be extra-cortical or a mixture of cortical and extra-cortical potentials. Accordingly, 'iso-electricity' results from tracing at (too) low sensitivity. But, a no detectable cortical activity (no-DCA)-EEG can be established when extra-cortical interferences are eliminated e.g. by neuromuscular blockade or identified e.g. by simultaneous recording of extracerebral activities of bio-electrical or bio-mechanical origin³⁶.

"A-reactive" EEG is emphasised without mentioning quantitative stimulation. Defined light-, sound- or noxious stimulation³³ should be applied to override stimuli from tubes, catheters, needles and 'noise' created by the ICU setting and, to ascertain that lack of responsiveness is reproducible.

*The inaccuracy of acknowledged PO-prognosticators such as no- or extensor MRP and BS-EEG is rooted in the fact that these signs may be transitory features of natural brain revival towards intact neurological survival (see table 1)*¹⁸.

"Multimodal" approaches to predicting PO

CG suggest the use of more clinical and/or paraclinical PO tests in combinations at 72 h from ROSC or later (72 h after re-warming) to minimise the probability of false outcome assignments and untimely limiting or withdrawal of life-sustaining support.

European Guidelines² suggest deploying an algorithm at 72 h or later - provided that patients are unconscious defined by no- or an extensor MRP. PO is considered "very likely" when the pupillary light- and/or the corneal reflex or the N20 wave of SSEP is absent. If such "robust" PO signs are not there it is recommended to wait at least 24 h and then assess outcome by two or more less accurate prognosticators. The approach is backed by studies of poor qE and provides indirect evidence only because it depends on solitary continuous variables. Odds ratios at each algorithmic step are not calculated and the scheme seems so far not tested in practice.

Brain imaging or serum marker-measurements have been selectively and rarely used. These paraclinical tests may not improve precision as they depict structural damages that are not consistently related to brain dysfunction.

Confounding factors

CG state that possible confounding factors (e.g. haemodynamic-, respiratory-, metabolic derangements and medication) should be taken into account before the outcome is decisively assessed. But, CG do not describe how such factors influence the brain resuscitation course. It has been shown that cardiovascular- or pulmonary complications relate to persistent unconsciousness and brain death³⁹.

Good outcome studies

CA-ischaemia has been conceived to produce clinical signs of static brain dysfunction, which *per se* qualified the neurological outcome –similar to the impact of primary brain lesions³². Consequently, neuroprognosis was estimated from signs or tests performed at random times, neurological findings were graded in a worst to best order^{32,40-43} and EEG classified by the 'degree of abnormality'^{44,45}. However, signs currently claimed signs to predict PO may be indistinguishable from intermittent features of GO e.g. no- or extensor MRP or no- or BS EEG as emphasized above (Table 1)¹⁸.

Most studies defined GO by CPCS 1-2 (: no or minor disabilities after awakening)¹⁵. *Classification by mRS was not used in the studies we reviewed.* The use of *solitary GO prognosticators* is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Prognosticators Of 'Good' Outcome Of PostCA Unconsciousness In NoTH-patients And In Patients Before, During And After TH

TEST	Total N of patients / noTH or before-during or off TH	p, prospective study r, retrospective study	Predictor	True positive rate (95% CI)	reference
Neurological examination					
CNR during BLS	111 / no	p	pupillary light at 7 min (5-12) ciliospinal at 13 min (10-26)	.85 (.51-.88) 1.0 (.85-.1.0)	17
CNR	192 / no/ before-off	p	2 or more of 5 CNR within 24 h	.83 (.77-.89)	46
total GCS score	133 / no	p	10 or more at 2 days	.77 (?)	43
total GCS score motor score	72 / off	p	>4 at day one off sedation, >6 thereafter >3 at day one	.90 (?) .92 (?) .43 (?)	47
motor score	302 / before	p	4-5 on admission	.87 (?)	48
Conventional EEG					
solitary conventional EEG	54 / during-off 200 / during	r r	grade 1(-2) grade 1 < 12 h	? 1.0 (.76-1.0)	49 50
	103 / off	p	'benign' EEG at 2-4 days	.48 (.31-66)	51

TEST	Total N of patients / noTH or before-during or off TH	p, prospective study r, retrospective study	Predictor	True positive rate (95% CI)	reference
continuous conventional EEG	34 / before-during-off	p	'reactivity' <24 h	.89 (?)	52
	200 / during	r	'reactivity' < 12 h	1.0 (?)	50
	56 / before-during-off	p	CCA at 12 h	.43 (?)	53
	388 / before-during-off	p	CCA at 12 h	.81 (.70-.88)	54
	109 / before-during-after	p	qEEG CRI >.69 at 24 h	1.0 (.54-1.0)	57
	277 / before-during-off	p	CCA at 12 h	.92 (.80-.98)	55
	100 /before-during-off	p	CCA at 6 - 72 h	.72 (.55-.88)	56
Automated EEG					
amplitude-integrated EEG	95/ during-off	p	CCA 'initially' or off TH	.90 (?) .87 (?)	58
	55 / before-during-off	p	'initial' or persistent cont. 'normal' voltage	.96 (?)	59
	130 /before-during-off	p	'normal' voltage trace <24 h	.88 (.77-.95)	60
	30 / before-during-off	r	cont. 'normal voltage' <23 h	1.0 (.71-1.0)	61
Bispectral index					
single test	65/during	p	20.5 <3h from ROSC	.82 (.61-.93)	62

TEST	Total N of patients / noTH or before-during or off TH	p, prospective study r, retrospective study	Predictor	True positive rate (95% CI)	reference
test every 30 min	96/during	p	23 after 12.5h	.89 (?)	63
SSEP					
Short-latency SSEP Middle-latency SSEP	46/during	r	N20/P25 or >.05 uV waves after 40-70 ms <72h	1.0(.80-1.0) 1.0 (.87-1.0)	64

Legend to Table 3. Prognosticators Of 'Good' Outcome Of Post-CA Unconsciousness In NoTH-patients And In Patients Before, During And After TH

Neurological examination

Investigations of CNR during BLS¹⁷ or total GCS after ROSC⁴³ were used to predict *recovery of consciousness*
Recovery of CNR < 24 h found valid if initial ventricular fibrillation and ROSC < 20 min⁴⁶

Conventional EEG

Solitary conventional EEG was graded 1-3 (3 most abnormal) by departmental developed scale⁴⁹ or by ACNS criteria if SSEP present⁵⁰,

"Benign" EEG was defined by no highly "malignant" (< 10uV activity or BS) nor "malignant" features (abundant or periodic rhythmic spikes and sharpwaves or unequivocal "seizures" or discontinuous or <20 uV or "areactive" background)⁵¹

Continuous conventional EEG with "reactivity" was defined by any reproducible change of CCA background following stimulation^{50,52}

CCA found a valid predictor if "positive" clinical signs and SSEP present⁵⁵

CCA >20 uV without 'epileptic' discharges found valid if more clinical signs are present⁵⁶

Quantitative EEG (qEEG) is grading continuous EEG by power, entropy, alpha to delta ratio, regularity and delta coherence extracted from 5 min epochs per h and quantified to produce a single number (cerebral recovery index (CRI)) 0: death, 1: full recovery)⁵⁷

Automated EEG

Amplitude- integrated EEG is genuine scalp EEG filtered, and 2-15 Hz activities processed into time-compressed displays of amplitudes achieving more hrs of surveillance per screen⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰

Bispectral index and suppression rate (BIS +SR) are based on frontal high-frequency EEG samples with intervals of few msec and 15-sec analyses of amplitude, frequency; phase-processed into numbers from 0: (low voltage) to 100. SR depicts % time of low voltage in BS^{62,63}

SSEP

Somatosensory evoked potentials are scalp signals provoked by 10 mA (short latency) and 50 mA(middle latency) stimulation – was claimed valid if neurological signs and EEG present to predict *recovery of consciousness*⁶⁴

Test sensitivities

In grade 4 and 5 studies *test sensitivities* were not given in two^{51,64}, .51-.84, depending on timing, in one⁴⁷ and .79-.96 in eight^{17,46,47,54,58,60,62,63}.

? data not available

Comments on solitary GO prognosticators

Table 3 shows that 17 clinical signs were claimed valid to predicting GO at or within 24 h, 11 of them at or within 12 h from CA!

Four studies of more prognosticators were without emphasis on the linkages between specific neurological and neurophysiological signs^{46,55,56,64}. One study grouped patients according to concurrent neurological and EEG findings but did not consider the prognostic aspect of the approach⁵⁸.

Rating study quality of evidence

qE grades were 1 (very high), 2 (high), 3 (moderate), 4 (low) and 5 (very low) depicting the confidence in a given prognosticator based on analyses of study design, conduct and reporting.

All studies were observational, and a priori downgraded one level of qE. Study quality was lowered further one level if we found a limiting factor in study design/execution, in prognosticator-/outcome-measures or identified an inconsistency or imprecision or a possible sample bias.

Studies were downgraded two levels if two or more drawbacks were established within the same category of limitations.

Study limitations and qE grades of the 21 studies are shown in Table 4.

Study design/execution limitations were investigation in retrospect, small sample sizes and testing only once (disregarding possible changes over time) or using single parameters only.

Inconsistencies were lack of identifying the heterogeneity of 'coma' (clinical features not specified), use of not-standardized tests or not-quantified stimuli or lack of standard interpretation of test results and of outcomes.

Imprecisions manifested by lack of focus on joint clinical features or lack of exact timing of prognostic tests or of the time to establish long-term neurological outcome at best (approval of possible 'surrogate' outcomes) or by lack of 'blinding' carers, investigators and evaluators to test results and/or patient outcomes.

A *sample bias* due to recruiting individuals that were 'not truly' unconscious⁴⁰ (about-to or already-awake, with inherently high odds of 'fair' neurological prospects) was suspected when the GO-rate exceeded 40%.

Table 4. Quality Of Evidence Rating Of 'Good' Outcome Studies

Ref	Design/execution		Inconsistencies			Impressions				S.bias	qE		
	Retrospective study	N <60	Study not longitudinal	Coma not defined	Tests not standard	'GO' not defined by CPC 1-2	Time from CA or ROSC to study not stated	Quantified stimuli not used	Time of outcome prediction not stated	< 6 months follow up	No blinding	'GO' rates >40%	Quality grade
17						X				X	X		4
46				X	X		X	X	X	X	X		5

Ref	Retrospective study	N <60	Study not longitudinal	Coma not defined	Tests not standard	'GO' not defined by CPC 1-2	Time from CA or ROSC to study not stated	Quantified stimuli not used	Time of outcome prediction not stated	< 6 months follow up	No blinding	'GO' rates >40%	Quality grade
43				X				X	X	X	X		4
47				X				X	X	X	X	X	5
48			X		X	X	X	X		X	X		>5
49	X	X		X	X		X	X	X	X		?	>5
50	X		X		X			X			X		>5
51			X				X	X	X				4
52		X		X	X		X	X		X	X	X	>5
53		X		X			X	X			X	X	>5
54					X			X				X	4
57				X	X			X			X	X	>5
55				X	X	X	X	X			X	X	>5
56				X		X		X	X	X	X	X	>5
58					X		X	X				X	5
59		X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X	>5
60					X			X	X			X	5
61	X	X			X			X	X	X	X	X	>5
62			X	X			X	X			X		5
63				X			X	X			X	X	5
64	X	X	X	X		X					X		5

Legend to Table 4. Quality Of Evidence Rating Of 'Good' Outcome Studies

Symbols

x, qE-limiting factor present , ? data not available

Column Headings

Study design/ execution

Three studies were *retrospective* (2 cEEG^{49,50} and 1 SSEP⁶⁴).

N of patients ranged from 30 to 388. *Sample size was < 60 patients* in 5 EEG and 1 SSEP study, 65-200 in 12 (2 CNR, 2MRP, 3 cEEG, 3 aEEG,2 BIS)^{17,43,46,47,50,51,56,58-60,62,63} and 277, 302 and 388 patients (1 MRP⁴⁸ , 2 cEEG^{54,55}).

Five studies (1 MRP⁴⁸ ,2 cEEG^{52,53}, 1 BIS study⁶² and 1 SSEP⁶⁴) were *not longitudinal* .

Inconsistencies

Patients were described as *comatose without specification of clinical features* in 13 studies. Coma was defined by CNR- or MRP findings in 7 studies (1 CNR¹⁷, 1 MRP⁴⁸, 3 cEEG^{50,51,54}, 2 aEEG^{58,60} and in one by absent response to verbal commands⁶¹.

Long-term neurological outcome was defined by CPCS 1-2 in all but 5 studies (defined by recovery of consciousness in 1 CNR, 1 MRP, 2 cEEG, 1 SSEP^{17,48,55,56,64} and not specified in 1 cEEG⁵⁵).

(Use of *standard tests* in 9 studies (1 CNR, 2 MRP, 3 cEEG, 2 BIS, 1 SSEP)^{17,43,47,49,50,55,61,64}, comparison of test results to *modelled reference standards* in 4 (2 CNR, 1 MRP, 1 qEEG)^{17,43,46,57}, and use of *quantitative stimulation* tests in 1 CNR and 1 SSEP study^{17,64} did not increase qE of the studies in question).

Imprecisions

The exact *time lapse reckoned from CA or ROSC* to the time of testing or to assessing outcome was not indicated in 10 studies (1 CNR⁴⁶, 1 MRP⁴⁸, 5 EEG^{49,51-53,55}, 1 aEEG⁵⁸ 2 BIS^{62,63}).

Long-term outcome was established at random or at arbitrarily chosen time points <6 months in 9 (1 CNR⁴⁶, 3 MRP^{43,47,48}, 3 cEEG^{49,52,56} 2 aEEG^{59,61}) and within or after 6 months in 12 studies.

('Blinding' in 6 studies (5 EEG, 1 BIS)^{49,51,54,58,60,63} did not increase study qE.)

Sample Bias (S.bias)

GO rates varied from 7 to 61%, in 7 studies up to 26% and in 13 studies from 37 to 61% (2 MRP, 6 cEEG, 4 aEEG, 1 BIS)^{43,47,52-61,63}. Rates were 46 to 61% 'at discharge' in 4 (1 MRP, 2 EEG, 1 BIS)^{47,55,59,61} and 41 to 61% within 2 to 6 months in 5 studies (5 EEG)^{52,54,57,60}.

Data were not available in one study⁴⁹.

Quality of evidence grades

Four studies (1 CNR¹⁷, 1 MRP⁴³, 2 cEEG^{51,54}) were of low qE (grade 4) and seven (1 CNR⁴⁶, 1 MRP⁴⁷, 2 aEEG^{58,60}, 2 BIS^{62,63}, 1 SSEP⁶⁴) of very low qE (grade 5). Ten studies (1 MRP, 7 cEEG, 2 aEEG) had more than five limitations to quality.

Timing of GO prognostication by quality-study indicators

It seems possible to predict GO within 30 min from CA by measuring the appearance times of pupillary reflexes (one grade 4 study)¹⁷ or *at or within 12 h* when CCA-cEEG is traced (one grade 4 study)⁵⁴, or CCA recorded in aEEG or high voltage/low SR are found in BIS studies (three grade 5 studies)^{58,62,63}.

Presence of more than 2 CNR or of a 'normal' voltage in aEEG (two grade 5 studies)^{46,60} within or at 24 h were found predictive of GO.

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first critical appraisal of current guidelines to predicting 'poor' neurological outcome of CA in adults left unconscious after CA and, the first systematic review of reported bedside indicators of 'good' outcome.

The overall quality of neuroprognostication studies is low. CG emphasized the low quality at PO studies and this report documents the poor qE of O studies.

However, this report highlights that the rate, order and linkage of neurological and EEG recoveries can provide definite clues to predicting PO as well as GO early after CA : PO can be predicted at 1 h by incomplete recovery of CNR or within the first 24 h from CA by lack of linked neurological and EEG features or by the presence of persistent epileptic phenomena ^{14,17}.

During THect and rewarming lack of pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes or presence of epileptiform activities in the EEG signify serious brain dysfunction and most likely PO. But observation should be prolonged, prognostic investigations repeated and possible confounding factors excluded before estimation of neuroprognosis. It is important to realize that transient features of natural brain resuscitation may mimic PO signs and misconceptions lead to untimely limiting or withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment. After all, WLST is the main cause of death among hospitalised CA-patients ^{2,30,40}.

PO can be predicted with certainty *at any time post-ROSC* if patients - meeting preconditions- have no CNR and irreversible apnoea ^{14,28}.

GO can be anticipated in noTH-patients when recovery of CNR is complete *at ROSC* and subsequently if CNR are all retained when the complete MRP- and EEG-features emerge ¹⁸.

We presume that presence of pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes and presence or appearance of CCA - EEG *during THect and rewarming* signify patients with high odds of GO.

After rewarming when sedation and paralysis have weaned GO features should expectedly include complete recovery of CNR, appropriate motor responses to 'pain' and continuous cortical activity (CCA).

The world over thousands of adults are left unconscious after resuscitation from CA every day ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ and yet only 21 eligible reports on bedside GO prognosticators were identified ! Further studies are needed to validate the parameters to predicting GO given by the present report because it is the only one available and it is based on studies of low quality.

CA is diagnosed by unconsciousness and apnoea in the pulseless patient. But serial brain function tests are not part of post-arrest routines. Repeated CNR checks ought to be an integral part of BLS procedures to assess the brain recovery potential and, serial CNR-, MRP- and EEG-tests integrated into post-resuscitation care to gauge brain resuscitation courses ¹⁸.

Incomplete CNR recovery within 24 h from ROSC in noTH-patients or prior to TH ⁴⁶ or lack of pupillary and motor responses 48 h from disconnection of sedation at the end of rewarming ²³ has been claimed compatible with GO. In our experience GO-patients invariably recover all CNR during or just after BLS ^{14,17}.

In noTH-patients MRP similar to *GCS total scores* of 4-6 or *motor scores* of 1-3 are transient features of post-arrest unconsciousness; higher total scores (due to orienting eye movements, defensive MRP and ability to obey commands or answer simple questions) signify awake patients¹⁸. Total GCS scores >6^{43,47} or motor scores >3^{40,47,48} thus may depict individuals about-to or already-awake⁴⁰, with inherently high odds of 'fair' neurological prospects.

Electroencephalography should be promoted. Analysis of 208.000 cases of CA in the USA from 2006-12 revealed that nationwide less than 2% of patients had EEG performed⁶⁸.

Conventional EEG (cEEG) is time demanding. Simplification by *automation* is possible but rarely used. However, results from 4 *amplitude-integrated EEG* (aEEG) and 2 *bispectral index* (BIS+SR) studies are included in Tables 3 and 4 because of their appeal and applicability. Automated EEG picks up extra-cortical interferences like the cEEG, in TH-patients due to shivering in particular. Because displays of aEEG are time-compressed and BIS+SR numbered it is necessary to trace the matrix EEG intermittently to decipher on-going events.

There are shortcomings to all reported EEG prognosticators of GO:

A single 20-30 min spot check 'benign' EEG at median 77 hours from CA in TH-patients⁵¹ or cEEG grade 1-2 pattern during TH^{49, 50} or steady CCA without superimposed epileptic discharges⁵³⁻⁵⁶ or high 'cerebral recovery index'⁵⁷ or 'normal' aEEG⁵⁸⁻⁶¹ or high BIS with low SR values⁶²⁻⁶³, or CCA 'reactivity'^{49,50,52,69,70} may all signify that patients were 'not truly' unconscious at the time of study.

The 'reactivity' illustrated in one report⁵² appears similar to the response found in drowsy or closed-eye, awake individuals^{71,72}. 'Reactivity' during TH in 13 of 192 patients was in one study associated with recovery of CNR, MRP and consciousness - but did not forecast GO⁷⁰.

Nipple pinching or pinprick or fingernail- or supraorbital notch pressure⁷³ or 'noise'⁵² have been applied to provoke 'reactivity'. Quantifiable visual, auditory and noxious stimuli should be but are only exceptionally used^{17,33} to ascertain and reproduce 'reactivity'.

Previous research demonstrated that the order and time course of recovery of brain functions after CA are keys to neuroprognostication: Recovery rates of early restorable functions determine the extent and rate of subsequent recovery^{14,18}. Therefore, it seems reasonable to relate tests results to time indications reckoned from CA or ROSC^{17,47,50,54-57,59-61,64} rather than to arbitrarily chosen cut-off time points^{43,47,53-56} or time spans^{44,50,52,60-64}. Time-indicative phrases like 'as soon as possible' or 'on admission', 'within the first day' or 'daily', or 'at start of ' or 'during TH' or 'after re-warming' devaluate study quality.

Developments of CCA from low voltage (LV) or BS were observed in cEEG^{26,53,54,58}, quantitative EEG (qEEG) and aEEG investigations⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰ but the precise time at which the GO pattern appeared was not stated. However, these studies reinforce our description of the natural course of electrocortical recovery after CA (Table 1).

SSEP is expertise demanding and not generally accessible. But, standardized techniques and definitions and 'blind' interpretations could make SSEP useful⁷⁴. A systematic review of 41 articles on 'early-after-the-onset-of-coma' SSEP established that the rate of awakening with 'no' SSEP was 0% (0-1), with 'abnormal' 22% (17-26) and with 'normal' responses 52% (48-56%)⁷⁵. However, 'no' SSEP, like 'isoelectric' EEG, can be a product of too-low-sensitivity tracing³¹ and, detectable cortical responses may return with delay after CA as is seen in conventional or automated EEG tracings¹⁸.

Awakening from CA promises high odds of 'fair' outcomes¹⁴. Study qE was herein downrated if the reported GO rate exceeded 40%, We presumed that 'not truly unconscious' individuals were enrolled. GO rates were 42 - 60% in 10 of 14 EEG studies⁵²⁻⁶¹ and 48% in one BIS study⁶³. Previous studies established 13 and 17% GO rates in noTH-^{18,42} and 9.9% in TH-patients⁴⁰. A large-scale investigation of the mere survival-to-discharge incidences disclosed 2 -10% rates after out-of-hospital arrest⁶⁶ and 22% after in-hospital arrest⁶⁷, the latter with a GO-rate of 16%.

All but five studies^{17,43,55,56,58} characterised GO by *CPCS 1-2*⁶ that defines post-awakening outcome by care dependency and lack of social adaptability (not necessarily reflecting neurological disorders) and, by the ability to resume daily life activities and work (not excluding severe neurological deficits). *mRS was not used in the studies we reviewed.*

We evaluated patient's ability to stand, walk and talk, to control bladder and gut and their awareness of own data, time, place and role of other persons and retention and recall to categorize outcomes by severe- or moderate- or slight/no disabilities¹⁸. However, neither this nor other function capacity schemes do capture what really matters to individuals in terms of acceptable and meaningful outcomes. Some may be content with their life after CA although left with neurological deficits which to others seem severely handicapping. A combination of repeated function capacity-¹⁸ and health related quality of life (HRQL)⁷⁶-measurements would be expected to refine the categorization of long-term neurological outcomes.

Postawakening faculties return successively. Repeated checks are needed to gauge the brain recovery course and to disclose complicating factors that may modify recovery decisively¹⁸. Patients should be given the chance and time to recover their faculties *at best* and outcomes be classified by patient's peak performances. Follow-ups 'at discharge' or at other arbitrarily chosen time points after CA may establish but 'surrogate' outcomes. In the noTH-patients we studied severe- or moderate- or slight/no disability at best was established after observation periods of 6 months, 128 and 90 days, respectively^{14,18}. *Similar data for TH-patients are not available.*

Suggested strategies

Table 5 summarizes current neuroprognostication practices or proposed approaches and the strategies we suggest. Care-professionals are accustomed to cope with monitoring tasks and can learn to check and document CNR-, MRP-, and EEG-signs over time.

Neurological tests are inexpensive, easily taught, applicable and documented e.g. by cell phone- or iPad-videos. EEG traced from a few scalp leads will do in most cases because the post-arrest EEG main-patterns (noDCA, BS, CCA and epileptic activities) usually are global.

Table 5. Current Neuroprognostication Practices or Proposed Approaches and Suggested Future Strategies

Current practices or proposed approaches	Suggested future strategies
Tools	
CNR, MRP, EEG, brain imaging, biomarkers, CPCS, mRS and HRQL	CNR+MRP+EEG , post-awakening neurological faculties and HRQL
Design and execution	
	Perform protocol driven large scale studies (include more ICUs) Categorize CA by aetiology Recruit patients in coma defined by distinctive neurological and EEG features at start of study
Use of independent clinical and/or paraclinical signs in combination	Establish linked clinical features
Dichotomy of outcome into 'poor' or 'good'	Discriminate between and among subgroups of 'poor' and 'good' neurological outcomes
Characteristics, execution and interpretation of index tests not consistently defined	Use standardized tests and well-defined keys to investigate and interpret clinical features
	Record the time of indicator testing reckoned from CA or ROSC
	Check CNR including measurements of pupillary sizes following light- and 'pain'-stimulation during BLS
	Test CNR + MRP + EEG during postROSC unconsciousness (pupillary reflexes + EEG during THect and rewarming (other CNR and MRP, when feasible))
Account for confounding factors	Specify possible influence from haemodynamic and/or respiratory and/or metabolic derangements and/or medication on neurological and/or EEG features
	Test for irreversible apnoea (if CNR are absent and preconditions met) to establish (brain stem) death.

Nipple pinching, pinprick, fingernail- or supraorbital notch pressure or 'noise'- stimulation used	Use defined, quantitative visual-,auditory and 'noxious' stimuli
	Account for WLST, brain- or cardiac death
	'Blind' carers/ investigators and evaluators to test results and neurological outcomes, when possible

Timing

Assessments of 'poor' outcome at 72 h or later and of 'good' outcome within 24 h	Establish brain stem death <i>at any time after ROSC</i> , when preconditions are met
	Estimate the brain recovery capability <i>during BLS</i> and <i>at ROSC</i> by the neurological findings
	Identify neuroprognostic clues <i>within the first h after CA</i> by repeated (optimally min per min) CNR testing
Single tests used once at random or at arbitrarily chosen time points	Discriminate likely 'poor' from likely 'good' outcome <i>within the first 24 h from ROSC</i> by repeat of (optimally hourly) CNR + MRP + EEG tests (by pupillary reflex- and EEG investigations <i>during THect</i>)
	<p>After <i>more than 24 h</i> post-ROSC test CNR+ MRP + EEG optimally more times daily in noTH-patients still unconscious (pupillary reflexes and EEG (other CNR and MRP, when feasible) <i>during THect and rewarming</i>)</p> <p>After <i>more than 72 h</i> repeat CNR+ MRP + EEG tests optimally every day during the first week if patients are unconscious</p> <p>Perform <i>ad hoc</i> neurological and EEG tests whenever interferences with brain recovery due to confounding factors are suspected</p>
Long-term neurological outcome measurements at arbitrarily chosen fixed time points	Survey return of post-awakening faculties optimally <i>once per week</i> to establish patient's neurological performances and 'quality of life' <i>at best</i>

Impact

	<p>Achieve clues to neuroprognosis within min from CA and within a few h after ROSC</p> <p>Identify treatment beneficiaries at or within a few h from ROSC</p>
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Ascertain that the brain recovery course is natural or derailed and, estimate treatment efficacy and interference from confounding factors during post-arrest unconsciousness

Refine categorization of short- and long-term neurological outcomes

Legend to table 5. Current Neuroprognostication Practices or Proposed Approaches and Suggested Future Strategies

The tools, design and execution, timing of current neuroprognostication practices or proposed approaches and suggested future strategies and the expected impacts of changed strategies.

Conclusion

Current neuroprognostication guidelines focus exclusively on predicting PO of post-CA unconsciousness by static clinical and/or paraclinical tests 3-5 days after ROSC and do not mention indicators of GO. Based on evidence from the literature we suggest updating guidelines by inclusion of early-after-CA bedside tests to monitor the brain resuscitation course and predict PO or GO.

We have emphasized herein that CNR findings during BLS and at ROSC depicts the brain recovery potential and define coma, neurological and EEG features during the very first min to hours of post-arrest unconsciousness provide definite clues to predicting neuroprognosis and may ease decisions on treatment strategies and that the peak of recovery of neurological faculties or patient's performances at best after awakening is a rational neuroprognostication endpoint. The overall qE of existing studies of 'poor' and 'good' neuroprognosticators is low. Future studies of the neuroprognosis after CA should embrace sizeable, standardized and longitudinal investigations of clinical parameters that relate directly to neurological outcomes.

Abbreviations

CA, cardiopulmonary arrest with global body ischaemia
BLS, basic life support
THect, therapeutic hypothermia with sedation, analgesia and neuromuscular blockade
CG, current neuroprognostication guidelines
PO, 'poor' outcome
GO, 'good' outcome
qE, quality of evidence
CNR, cranial nerve reflex
MRP, motor response to 'pain'
GCS, Glasgow Coma Scale
ROSC, re-establishment of spontaneous circulation
EEG, electroencephalogram
NoDCA, no detectable cortical activity
LV, low voltage
BS, bursts-suppressions
CCA, continuous cortical activity
aEEG, amplitude integrated EEG
qEEG, quantitative EEG

ACNS, American Clinical Neurophysiological Society
BIS+SR, bispectral index
SSEP, somatosensory evoked potential
WLST, withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment
TPR, true positive rate
CPCS, Cerebral Performance Category Scale
mRS, modified Rankin Scale
HRQOL, health related quality of life

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